

Nature of Phenoxides of Phosphorus(V)

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Compounds of composition $P(OC_6H_5)_nCl_{5-n}$ ($n=1-5$) have been prepared by the reaction of phosphorus(V) chloride and phenol in appropriate molar ratio in carbon tetrachloride under different experimental conditions. Molecular weight and ir spectral studies show them to be monomers. Double phenoxides of composition $M'[M(OC_6H_5)_6]$, ($M=P$; $M'=Li, Na$ or K) have also been prepared by reacting alkali metal phenoxides and phosphorus pentaphenoxide in 1 : 1 molar ratio which is supported by conductometric titrations in phenol. Reactions with acetyl chloride and hydrogen chloride to get back the original phosphorus chlorides have also been attempted.

LIKE alkoxides, metal phenoxides find many industrial applications¹, but surprisingly very little attention has been focussed on them. Alkoxide derivatives of some electronegative elements are non-ionic, highly volatile and monomeric²⁻¹⁰. The high electronegativity of the central atom and also the extensive intra-molecular $p\pi-d\pi$ contribution impart the covalent character prevailing in these alkoxides and it is effected by the size of the central atom. In view of these interesting observations and increasing industrial uses of phenoxides of metals and non-metals, it is, therefore, of interest to isolate and characterise phenoxides of phosphorus(V). Interest is also focussed on their formation of double phenoxides.

Experimental

The reagents were purified by the standard methods and used immediately after purification. All the organic solvents (AnalaR) were further dried by appropriate drying agents and finally fractionally distilled before used.

Compound of composition $PCl_4(OC_6H_5)$ was obtained by stirring a solution of phosphorus(V) chloride (4.0 g, 0.019 mol) and phenol (1.8 g, 0.019 mol) in carbon tetrachloride at room temperature for ~24 h till there was no evolution of HCl gas. In the case of compounds of composition $PCl_3(OC_6H_5)_2$ and $PCl_2(OC_6H_5)_3$, the reactants were refluxed in 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 molar ratio in carbon tetrachloride. The completion of the reaction was judged by the non-evolution of HCl. In preparation of phenoxide of composition $PCl(OC_6H_5)_4$ by refluxing phosphorus(V) chloride and phenol in 1 : 4 molar ratio in carbon tetrachloride, two different liquid layers of the solvent and the compound were separated out through separating funnel. However, in case of pentaphenoxide of phosphorus $P(OC_6H_5)_5$, the contents in 1 : 5 molar ratio were refluxed in presence of a base when a liquid layer of the compound so formed was obtained. The

compounds were washed repeatedly with carbon tetrachloride and finally dried under vacuum.

Double phenoxides of composition $M'[P(OC_6H_5)_6]$, ($M=Li, Na$ or K) were obtained by refluxing the components in 1 : 1 molar ratio in carbon tetrachloride till the components dissolved. The components were isolated by cooling the solution supplemented by the addition of petroleum ether.

Phosphorus was estimated as magnesium pyrophosphate, and chlorine by Volhard's method. Infrared spectra (nujol/KBr) of the compounds were scanned on a Perkin-Elmer 337 (400-4000 cm^{-1}) and a Perkin-Elmer 621 (200-600 cm^{-1}) spectrophotometers. Molecular weights of the phenoxide were determined cryoscopically in benzene by Beckmann method.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometric composition of the phenoxides isolated in the present study is reported in Table 1. All these compounds are moisture-sensitive but are sufficiently stable in dry air. They are soluble in most of the polar organic solvents. Molar conductance values of $10^{-3} M$ solutions of all these phenoxides except double phenoxides, suggest that they are non-electrolytes. Double phenoxides of composition $M'[M(OC_6H_5)_6]$ have very high molar conductance values which indicate their ionic nature. Molecular weight determinations of the phenoxides of composition $P(OC_6H_5)_5$, $PCl(OC_6H_5)_4$, $PCl_2(OC_6H_5)_3$ and $PCl_3(OC_6H_5)_2$ suggest them to be monomers at low as well as at higher concentrations; while the phenoxide $PCl_4(OC_6H_5)$ is a monomer at low concentrations, but at higher concentrations it has a tendency to associate.

Informations on the structure and stereochemistry of the compounds of composition $P(OC_6H_5)_5$, $PCl(OC_6H_5)_4$, $PCl_2(OC_6H_5)_3$, $PCl_3(OC_6H_5)_2$ and $PCl_4(OC_6H_5)$ have been obtained by their infrared studies. In the ir spectra of these phenoxides

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA AND PRINCIPAL IR SPECTRAL BANDS (cm⁻¹) OF PHENOXIDES OF PHOSPHORUS(V)

Compd.	Colour	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		Molar conductance in nitro- benzene Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹	Molecular weight in nitrobenzene Found**/ (Calcd.)	ν _{O-C}	ν _{P-O}	ν _{P-Cl}
			P	Cl					
PCl ₄ (OC ₆ H ₅)	White	127	11.63 (11.65)	53.36 (53.38)	2.8	271 (266)	1178, 1167	982, 978	446
PCl ₃ (OC ₆ H ₅) ₂	White	87	9.57 (9.58)	32.93 (32.90)	3.3	— (323.5)	1171, 1165	980, 971	443
PCl ₂ (OC ₆ H ₅) ₃	White	78	8.22 (8.26)	18.92 (18.93)	3.1	387 (381)	1172, 1170	984, 978	445, 440
PCl(OC ₆ H ₅) ₄	Colourless	89*	7.04 (7.06)	8.06 (8.09)	1.8	442 (438.5)	1167	982, 976	442
P(OC ₆ H ₅) ₅	Colourless	187*	6.27 (6.25)	—	2.6	498 (494)	1168, 1175	980, 972	—

* Boiling point. ** Mean value of three determinations.

the broad band in the region 3650-3590 cm⁻¹, assigned to hydrogen bonded phenolic hydroxy group in pure phenol¹³, is altogether missing in all the compounds, which is also supported by the observation that hydrogen chloride gas is liberated during the course of their preparation. The most important and strong band at 1230 cm⁻¹ in pure phenol due to ν_{C-O} stretching mode, shifts to lower spectral regions by about 50-60 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of these compounds. This shift may be attributed to the attachment of phenolic oxygen to the central phosphorus atom. The important bands are given in Table 1. The bands in the region 980-970 cm⁻¹ (not present in pure phenol) may be assigned to active P-O stretching modes¹⁴. It is interesting to note that in these compounds no bands around 900 and 1250 cm⁻¹, that could be assigned to P-O-P and P=O stretching modes, respectively¹⁵⁻¹⁷ have been observed suggesting that there is neither oxygen abstraction nor any

polymerization through P $\begin{matrix} / \\ \backslash \end{matrix}$ O $\begin{matrix} / \\ \backslash \end{matrix}$ P bridging.

Apart from the usual bands expected for phenoxide formation in the case of phenoxides of composition PCl₄(OC₆H₅), PCl₃(OC₆H₅)₂, PCl₂(OC₆H₅)₃ and PCl(OC₆H₅)₄, intense and sharp bands in the region 440-450 cm⁻¹ and not found in the case of compound of composition P(OC₆H₅)₅, may be assigned to the terminal phosphorus chlorine stretching modes^{18,19}. No band which could be assigned to bridged chlorine is observed. Thus based upon ir spectral studies and molecular weight determinations, it is possible to assign monomeric trigonal bipyramidal structure for these compounds.

A number of references are available in literature concerning the isolation and characterisation of double salts. Recently, Mehrotra *et al.*²⁰ have successfully prepared niobium and tantalum double isopropoxides of the type MM'(OPrⁱ)₆ and MM'₂(OPrⁱ)₁₁, where M' = Nb or Ta and M = Al, Ga. Therefore, in the present investigations, double phenoxides of phosphorus of composition M'[P(OPh)₅], where M = Li, Na or K, have been prepared by refluxing phosphorus(V) phenoxide and

the alkali metal phenoxides in predetermined molar ratio in carbon tetrachloride. Stoichiometry of these compounds was established by elemental analysis and further confirmed by carrying out conductometric titrations of the solvo acid P(OPh)₅ against solvo bases in phenol at 50 ± 0.1°. A sharp break in the conductance composition curve at the molar ratio 1 : 1 confirms the formation of a double phenoxide according to the reaction,

In general, the more basic phenoxide transferred its phenoxide groups to the more acidic phenoxide through a complex ion involving the element in its higher coordination number.

Metal chlorides can be regenerated easily by reacting metal phenoxides with excess hydrogen chloride or acetyl chloride. Mehrotra *et al.* have isolated compounds of composition GeCl₄ and Ti(OPh)₅.Cl.PhOH by the reaction of hydrogen chloride with phenyl-*ortho*-germanate²¹ and phenyl-*ortho*-titanate²², respectively. Last of all, an attempt has been made to get back the phosphorus chlorides by reacting phosphorus(V) phenoxide with hydrogen chloride and acetyl chloride under different experimental conditions. Reaction of phosphorus penta-phenoxide in benzene with hydrogen chloride at room temperature yields a compound of composition PCl₂(OC₆H₅)₃. It was identified by elemental analysis and its sharp melting point (78°). A possible reaction showing its formation may be postulated as

In case of acetyl chloride, its conductometric titrations with phosphorus(V) phenoxide in nitrobenzene show three sharp breaks at 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 in the conductance-composition curve. This can be rationalised in terms of following reactions.

However, in an attempt to replace fourth phenoxy group by refluxing $P(OC_6H_5)_5/CH_3COCl$ in 1 : 4 molar ratio or with excess of acetyl chloride, no new compound could be isolated.

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